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● *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov., a new species of *Oreasiobia* Semenov, 1936 (Dermaptera: Forficulidae) from China

Zhi-Teng CHEN

School of Grain Science and Technology, Jiangsu University of Science and Technology, Zhenjiang 212004, Jiangsu Province, China;

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6331-8978>; 741208116@qq.com

Abstract: A new species of the forficulid genus *Oreasiobia* Semenov, 1936, *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov., is described and illustrated from Meri Snow Mountain, Yunnan Province, China. The new species is characterized by the well-developed tegmina and wings, absence of projections on ultimate tergite, a long pygidium, and almost straight forceps with a subtriangular basal tooth.

Keywords: Biodiversity, earwigs, morphology, new species, taxonomy

● 中国山球螋属一新种——梅里山球螋（革翅目：球螋科）

陈志腾

粮食学院，江苏科技大学，镇江 212004，江苏省，中国

摘要：本文描绘了一个产于中国云南省梅里雪山的山球螋属 *Oreasiobia* Semenov, 1936 新种——梅里山球螋 *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov.。该新种具有以下特征：鞘翅和后翅发达；末腹背板无尖的突起；臀板较长；尾铗几乎笔直，基部具一近三角形大齿。

关键词：生物多样性，螋，形态学，新种，分类学

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Introduction

Oreasiobia Semenov, 1936 is a small earwig genus of the subfamily Anechurinae within family Forficulidae. To date, six species of *Oreasiobia* have been recognized from Central Asia, including *Oreasiobia calciatii* (Borelli, 1909), *Oreasiobia chinensis* Steinmann, 1974, *Oreasiobia fedtschenkoi* (de Saussure, 1874), *Oreasiobia forcipina* Yang & Zhang, 1988, *Oreasiobia piger* Steinmann, 1983, and *Oreasiobia similis* Steinmann, 1983. Among which, *O. chinensis*, *O. fedtschenkoi*, and *O. forcipina* have been recorded in China (Chen & Ma 2004; Srivastava 2013). Another previously known species, *Oreasiobia stoliczkae* (Burr, 1911), was synonymized with *Anechura stoliczkae* Burr, 1911 by Srivastava (2013).

In this study, a new species of *Oreasiobia* from Meri Snow Mountain, Yunnan Province, China is described and illustrated. The new species is compared with all congeners for distinguishment. This work endeavors to enhance our comprehension of earwig biodiversity in China and make substantive contributions to the field of insect taxonomy and conservation.

Material and methods

The specimens examined in this study were hand-collected from China and preserved in 99% ethanol. The observations were conducted utilizing a SDPTOP SZM45 stereo microscope, with color images captured using a Canon EOS 6D digital camera equipped with a Canon MP-E 65 mm 5X macro lens. All images were processed and compiled into plates using Adobe Photoshop (Beta).

The types are deposited in the Insect Collection of Jiangsu University of Science and Technology (ICJUST), located in Jiangsu Province, China. Terminology follows that of Steinmann (1993).

Taxonomy

Oreasiobia meria sp. nov. 梅里山球螋

<https://zoobank.org/33538D09-2724-423A-92CA-5A4FE8636B9E>

Figs. 1–3

Type material. Holotype: ♂ (ICJUST), **CHINA, Yunnan:** Deqin County, Meri Snow Mountain, Mingyong Glacier (Fig. 1), 28.46753146°N, 98.78244725°E, 2350 m, 6.IV.2021, Zhi-Teng Chen.

Etymology. The new species is named after its type locality in Meri Snow Mountain, Yunnan Province, China.

Description. Male. Body mostly dark brown; head, tegmina, and scale of hindwing black (Fig. 2). Length without forceps 13.5 mm, length of forceps 10 mm.

Head. Head subquadrate (Fig. 2), slightly longer than wide, frontal and epicranial sutures distinct, posterior margin truncate. Eyes small, subequal to half the length of head behind eyes. Antennae 12-segmented; antennomere 1 short, slightly shorter than distance between antennal bases; antennomere 2 very short, near as long as wide; antennomere 3 distinctly longer than antennomere 4; antennomere 5 slightly longer than antennomere 3; subsequent antennomeres slender.

Thorax. Pronotum as wide as head (Fig. 2), transverse, wider than long, anterior margin straight, lateral margins gradually converging, posterior margin rounded. Tegmina well-developed, length about two times longer than width, lateral margins arc-shaped, posterior margin slightly concave. Scales of hindwings well-developed, near half of tegmina length, posterior margin truncate. Legs covered with dense yellow hairs, hind tarsomere 1 near two times longer than tarsomere 3.

Abdomen. Abdomen feebly dilated to 6th segment (Fig. 2); posterolateral glandular folds distinct on tergite 4, almost invisible on 3. Ultimate tergite transverse (Fig. 3A), about three times as wide as long, with two large, rounded humps near base of forceps. Pygidium specific (Fig. 3A, B), thick, longer than wide, broad at base, constricted subbasally, apical half semi-elliptical, obtuse, with deep posterolateral grooves caused by basal teeth of

forceps. Penultimate sternite broadly rounded. Branches of forceps distinctly elongated, with right-angled basolateral margins; branches with a subtriangular, obtuse basal tooth internally; inner margin of basal tooth denticulate; distal portion of forceps cylindrical in cross-section; both branches slightly curved at basal half, almost straight at apical half, apices pointed and incurved.

Genitalia. Genitalia elongated (Fig. 3C, D); central parameral plate elliptical, widened subapically; virga within genital lobe long, basal vesicle weakly sclerotized; external parameres slender, finger-shaped.

Female. Unknown.

FIGURE 1. *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov., habitat in Meri Snow Mountain, Yunnan Province, China.

Differential diagnosis. *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov. is easily distinguished from *O. calciatii*, *O. chinensis*, and *O. fedtschenkoi* by the absence of peg-shaped chitinous appendages on ultimate tergite (Steinmann 1993; Srivastava 2013). The new species is further separated from *O. similis* by the presence of well-developed tegmina and wings (Steinmann 1983). The almost straight forceps and the long pygidium of the new species differ from the strongly curved forceps and short pygidium in *O. piger* (Steinmann 1983). Finally, the new species is most similar to *O. forcipina* known from Guizhou Province of China (Yang & Zhang 1988). However, the new species can be distinguished from *O. forcipina* by the much longer antennomeres, longer tegmina and wings, and projected pygidium (Yang & Zhang 1988).

Distribution. China (Yunnan).

FIGURE 2. *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov., male holotype: **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** habitus, lateral view **C** habitus, ventral view. Scale bar = 5 mm.

FIGURE 3. *Oreasiobia meria* sp. nov., male holotype: **A** terminalia, dorsal view **B** terminalia, ventral view **C** genitalia, ventral view **D** genitalia, dorsal view. Scale bars = 1 mm for A, B, 0.5 mm for C, D.

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Additional information

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